

Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam Today

Tran Van Mong

Thu Dau Mot University

ABSTRACT: In the context of Vietnam's goal of becoming an upper-middle-income country by 2030 and a high-income country by 2045, the private sector is identified as a crucial driving force of the economy. However, the actual effectiveness of policies to develop the private sector still has certain limitations. This article applies a multi-tiered analytical framework based on the new institutional theory (North, 1990), the policy implementation theory (Mazmanian, 1972), and the enterprise absorption capacity theory (Cohen, 1990) to identify three groups of factors affecting policy effectiveness: (i) foundational institutions; (ii) policy implementation and public governance; and (iii) the absorption capacity of the private sector. Based on statistical data analysis and reports from the World Bank, OECD, and PCI, this study shows that Vietnam's private sector development policy is strategically sound and has created a more favorable business environment. However, its effectiveness in transforming into productivity growth and competitiveness remains at a moderate level due to a lack of synergy between institutional design, implementation quality, and enterprise internal capacity. This article proposes systemic solutions to improve policy effectiveness in the coming period.

KEYWORDS: private sector, policy effectiveness, institutions, policy implementation, public governance, absorption capacity.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of Vietnam entering a new stage of development with the goal of becoming an upper-middle-income country by 2030 and a high-income country by 2045, the private sector is identified as playing a central role in promoting growth, innovation, and enhancing national competitiveness. The 13th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam affirmed the requirement to “strongly develop the private economy to truly become an important driving force of the economy” (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). In fact, the non-state sector currently contributes about 42% of GDP and employs over 80% of the social workforce (General Statistics Office, 2023). However, a World Bank report shows that the labor productivity of domestic private enterprises is still significantly lower than that of the FDI sector; small and medium-sized enterprises account for the majority; The region's capacity to participate in global value chains and innovate remains limited (World Bank, 2022). Simultaneously, the new context of digital transformation, the demand for green development, the implementation of new-generation trade commitments (CPTPP, EVFTA), and the pressure to improve the business environment to international standards are posing significant challenges for this region (OECD, 2023). These factors highlight the urgent need to reassess the effectiveness of private sector development policies and identify influencing factors in the current context.

From a public policy science perspective, policy effectiveness is measured not only by the extent to which immediate goals are achieved but also by its ability to create sustainable impacts and improve the long-term quality of institutions (Dunn, 2018). North's (1990) institutional theory suggests that the institutional environment, including the legal system, property rights guarantees, and transparency, has a decisive influence on transaction costs and private sector investment incentives. Meanwhile, Mazmanian and Sabatier's (1972) policy implementation model emphasizes that the legal structure, clarity of objectives, and capacity of implementing agencies are key conditions determining policy outcomes. Combining these approaches, this paper aims to: (i) build a framework for analyzing the levels of factors affecting the effectiveness of private sector economic development policies; (ii) apply the theoretical framework to analyze the current situation in Vietnam in recent times. (iii) Proposing solutions to improve policies in the context of integration and digital transformation. Regarding research methodology, the article uses analysis (institutional analysis, policy cycle analysis), synthesis and comparison of statistical data from the General Statistics Office, World Bank and OECD, combined with comparative methods and logical reasoning to ensure the scientific validity and reliability of the arguments.

CONTENTS

1. Theoretical basis of factors affecting the effectiveness of private sector economic development policies

1.1. Concept of policy effectiveness in private sector economic development

In public policy science, policy effectiveness is measured not only by the degree to which immediate goals are achieved but also by the implementation costs, the sustainability of results, and the ability to create long-term institutional change (Dunn, 2018). According to this approach, the effectiveness of private sector economic development policies needs to be evaluated on three aspects: (i) the degree of improvement in the business environment and investment incentives; (ii) the increase in productivity and innovation of enterprises; and (iii) the spillover effects on growth and economic structure.

From the perspective of development economics, the private sector is considered the central driver of long-term growth due to its ability to allocate resources more efficiently and create incentives for innovation (World Bank, 2022). However, for this sector to fulfill its role, a prerequisite is an institutional environment that guarantees property rights, contracts, and fair competition. North (1990) argues that institutions are “man-made constraints that structure political, economic, and social interactions,” and that the quality of institutions determines transaction costs as well as long-term investment incentives. This implies that the effectiveness of policies for developing the private sector depends primarily on the quality of institutional design.

On the other hand, research on governance and growth by Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) shows that inclusive institutions, where property rights are protected and economic opportunities are expanded, have a positive impact on business and innovation incentives. Therefore, the effectiveness of policies for developing the private sector cannot be separated from the quality of the fundamental institutions of the economy.

From the above perspectives, it can be understood that policy effectiveness in the development of the private sector is the extent to which policies achieve the goals of promoting growth, improving productivity and competitiveness of businesses, while ensuring reasonable implementation costs and creating a sustainable impact on the institutional environment and economic structure.

1.2. Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Sector Economic Development Policies and the Basis for Selection

Identifying factors affecting the effectiveness of private sector economic development policies cannot be based on subjective reasoning, but must stem from a theoretical foundation and policy analysis models that have been validated in research. Based on a synthesis of the new institutional theory (North, 1990), the policy implementation model (Mazmanian, 1972), the public policy cycle (Dunn, 2018), and the theory of enterprise competitiveness (Porter, 1990), this paper selects three main groups of factors: (1) foundational institutions; (2) public implementation and governance capacity; (3) the absorption capacity of the private sector. This structure reflects the multi-layered logic of “design – implementation – absorption”, and is consistent with the systems analysis framework in policy research.

1.2.1. Institutional Factors as the Foundation

Placing institutions as the first group of factors is based on the foundation of new institutional economics. North (1990) argues that institutions are the “rules of the game” of society, determining the incentive structure and transaction costs. In a stable institutional environment, property rights are guaranteed and laws are transparent, businesses have the incentive to invest long-term and innovate. Conversely, when institutions are unstable or inconsistently implemented, transaction costs will increase and undermine policy effectiveness.

Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) further develop this argument by distinguishing between inclusive institutions and extractive institutions. Inclusive institutions create equal opportunities for businesses, thereby promoting competition and innovation. This is particularly important for private sector development policies, because if the competitive environment is not equal between the public and private sectors, support policies will not achieve the expected results.

Reports from the World Bank (2020), (2022) and OECD (2018), (2023) also show that improved institutional quality is strongly correlated with business productivity and the level of private sector formalization. Therefore, choosing institutions as the foundational layer is consistent with theoretical and empirical evidence.

1.2.2. Policy Implementation and Public Governance Factors

If institutions determine the dynamic structure, then implementation determines the ability to transform policies into results. Mazmanian and Sabatier (1972) argued that policy results depend on the clarity of objectives, the legal structure, and the capacity of the implementing agency. Research by Pressman and Wildavsky (1984) showed that when the implementation process goes through many administrative layers without coordination, the probability of achieving policy objectives decreases significantly.

In the current context, for a private sector development policy to achieve the desired results, tools such as credit support, administrative procedure reform, or tax incentives all require inter-sectoral and inter-level coordination. The OECD (2023), when evaluating SME policies in Vietnam, also emphasized that fragmentation in implementation can diminish the impact of policies. This shows that the selection of implementation factors is not only based on theory but also reinforced by practical evidence.

From the perspective of the policy cycle (Dunn, 2018), the implementation phase is a crucial link between policy design and evaluation. If this stage is weak, the entire cycle will be disrupted. Therefore, implementation factors are placed at an intermediate level in the analytical model.

Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam Today

1.2.3. The Absorption Capacity of the Private Sector

One of the limitations of many policy studies is that they focus only on the State side while neglecting the capacity of the beneficiaries. According to Cohen and Levinthal (1990), absorption capacity is the ability to identify, acquire, and apply new knowledge; this is a prerequisite for businesses to transform support into innovation. If businesses lack management capacity, have low-quality human resources, or are too small in scale, support policies will struggle to create long-term impacts.

Porter (1990), in his theory of national competitive advantage, also emphasized that the intrinsic capacity of businesses and the competitive environment determine the ability to improve productivity. Studies by the World Bank (2022) on Vietnam's private sector show that low productivity and weak linkages with the FDI sector are also major obstacles to sustainable growth.

Therefore, adding the group of business capacity factors to the analytical framework helps avoid a linear approach and fully reflects the systemic nature of the private sector development policy.

1.3. The Optimality of the Three-Group Factor Structure

The three-group factor structure is not a random list but is based on a multi-level system analysis model in public policy research. This approach has three layers: (i) the macro layer (institutions and legal environment); (ii) the meso layer (enforcement and governance mechanisms); and (iii) the micro layer (business capacity). This layering allows for the simultaneous assessment of structural and operational factors, while accurately reflecting the nature of the interaction between the State and the market. Focusing on only one layer (e.g., institutions) would result in a lack of practical depth in the analysis; focusing only on businesses would overlook long-term institutional dynamics. Therefore, the three-factor model is considered optimal for analysis because it ensures systematicity, theoretical continuity, and practical applicability.

2. The Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam According to a Three-Group Structure of Factors

2.1. Foundational Institutional Factors

In the context of deep international economic integration today, Vietnam affirms that the development of the private economy is an important driving force of the economy (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). This is a step forward in institutional awareness, creating a political foundation for reform. In practice, the 2020 Enterprise Law and the 2020 Investment Law have expanded the freedom of business and reduced the number of conditional business sectors. According to the General Statistics Office (2023), the non-state sector in 2023 contributed approximately 42–45% of GDP and employed over 80% of the total workforce. This shows that the policy has been effective at the level of market entry and expansion of the private sector (Nguyen Si Dung, 2025). The World Bank also noted Vietnam's significant improvements in its business environment and international integration (World Bank & MPI, 2016). This shows that Vietnam has improved the "official rules of the game," creating positive momentum for the private sector.

However, according to the World Bank (2020), the productivity of domestic private enterprises remains significantly lower than that of the FDI sector. This reflects the fact that institutional efficiency has not fully translated into growth. The PCI 2023 report shows that informal costs and significant disparities between localities in terms of transparency and access to land still exist (VCCI & USAID, 2023). According to North's (1990) argument, when institutions do not ensure predictability and transparency, transaction costs increase, reducing the incentive for long-term investment. The Government also acknowledges overlapping laws in areas such as land, investment, and construction as a bottleneck in reform. The main reasons are believed to be (i) the legal system is in the process of being perfected and adjusted, (ii) the inter-sectoral coordination mechanism is still limited, and (iii) policy stability and predictability are not high (Government, 2023).

Overall, it can be seen that in terms of fundamental institutional factors, the policy for developing the private economy in Vietnam has basically achieved effectiveness at the level of orientation and creating a general environment, but has not yet reached the level of "high-quality institutions" according to OECD standards (2023).

2.2. Policy Implementation and Public Governance Factors

Vietnam has strongly implemented administrative reforms and digital transformation in public governance, such as the National Public Service Portal integrating more than 4,000 online services; 100% of business registrations are conducted online; and the socio-economic recovery and development package for the period 2022–2023 (approximately VND 350 trillion) also demonstrated a rapid policy response to support businesses after the pandemic (Government, 2023). This is consistent with the "adaptive governance" approach, enhancing the effectiveness of policy responses.

However, implementation effectiveness remains uneven: the 2023 PCI index shows significant disparities between localities in terms of time costs and government dynamism (VCCI & USAID, 2023); The phenomenon of "avoiding responsibility" among a segment of officials and civil servants slows down the approval process of investment projects (Government, 2023). According to policy implementation theory, when the commitment and motivation of implementing agencies decrease, policy effectiveness will be limited (Mazmanian, 1972). The main reasons are believed to be (i) the public service evaluation system is not strongly linked to output results, (ii) the decentralization mechanism is not coupled with accountability, and (iii) the management culture is still

Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam Today

more focused on risk control than on facilitation. Therefore, this is considered the most significant factor in reducing the effectiveness of current private sector economic policies.

2.3. Factors influencing the private sector's absorption capacity

The number of newly established businesses remains high, the private sector contributes the majority of jobs, and several large private corporations have participated in global value chains in the technology, aviation, and automotive industries (General Statistics Office, 2023); Vietnam's innovation and startup ecosystem is ranked among the fastest-growing in Southeast Asia (World Bank, 2022).

However, over 95% of businesses are small and medium-sized enterprises (General Statistics Office, 2023). Domestic private sector labor productivity is significantly lower than that of FDI, the proportion of businesses investing in R&D is still low (World Bank, 2022), and linkages with FDI businesses are limited (OECD, 2023). This indicates weak policy absorption capacity, reducing the effectiveness of institutional transformation into high-quality growth. The reasons are believed to be: (i) limited capital and technology accumulation, (ii) the prevalence of family business management, and (iii) the underdeveloped long-term capital market. While Vietnam's current private sector development policy is on the right track strategically, its actual effectiveness remains low due to a lack of synergy between institutional reforms, implementation quality, and the internal strength of businesses.

3. Solutions to Enhance the Effectiveness of Private Sector Development Policies in Vietnam

Based on the current situation showing that the effectiveness of private sector development policies in Vietnam is still low and has not fully transformed into sustainable productivity growth, solutions need to be designed in a synchronized, systematic manner and based on the logical linkage between institutions – governance – market. Addressing individual bottlenecks will not be enough to create structural change; instead, reforms need to be approached at all three levels: (i) institutional foundation, (ii) implementation capacity, and (iii) enterprise internal strength.

3.1. Improving the foundational institutions towards enhancing quality and predictability

First, overcoming overlapping and unstable laws must be considered a priority for urgent institutional reform. The conflict between laws related to investment, land, construction, and planning not only increases compliance costs but also creates legal risks for investors. When the legal environment lacks consistency, businesses tend to delay long-term investments and prioritize short-term strategies to minimize risk. Therefore, a comprehensive review of the legal system regarding investment and business is needed, focusing on integration, eliminating duplication, and establishing inter-sectoral legal coordination mechanisms. Institutionalizing the Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) process in a substantive manner, with mandatory business consultation, will help reduce the risk of enacting unfeasible policies. Simultaneously, the principle of "one document amending multiple laws" should be applied flexibly to limit legal fragmentation and increase the consistency of the institutional system. The ultimate goal is to reduce transaction costs and improve the predictability of the investment environment.

Secondly, institutional reform needs to shift from the stage of "expanding business freedom" to building "high-quality institutions." This requires strengthening property rights protection, improving contract enforcement efficiency, and ensuring transparency in resource allocation. Publicizing planning, land, bidding, and public investment data on digital platforms not only reduces informal costs but also creates a level playing field for businesses. When institutions are transparent and verifiable, market confidence is strengthened, thereby promoting long-term investment and innovation.

Thirdly, in the context of deep integration and the transformation towards a green and digital economy, increasing stability and long-term policy commitment is crucial. Sudden policy changes can undermine investment incentives in strategic sectors such as renewable energy, high technology, or digital transformation. Therefore, it is necessary to build a mechanism for medium-term policy commitment, especially in national priority areas, while establishing an early warning system for policy changes and a mechanism for regular consultation with business associations. This solution aims to reduce institutional risk, a factor that has been identified as a significant obstacle to long-term private sector investment.

3.2. Enhancing Policy Implementation Effectiveness and Public Administration Quality

Practice shows that the biggest bottleneck today lies not in strategic direction but in implementation. The gap between policies on paper and policies in practice significantly reduces overall effectiveness.

First, reforming the system of evaluation and public service motivation is a prerequisite for overcoming the avoidance of responsibility. When the evaluation system is not closely linked to output results and the level of satisfaction of businesses, the motivation for reform will decrease. Therefore, it is necessary to strongly shift to a results-based evaluation mechanism, in which indicators such as processing time, disbursement rate, and level of business satisfaction become core criteria. At the same time, the responsibility of the head of the agency needs to be clearly defined and linked to the progress of policy implementation. In parallel, the mechanism for protecting officials who dare to think and act must be improved, avoiding the situation where "legal security" stifles innovation in the public sector.

Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam Today

Next, decentralization must go hand in hand with accountability. The significant disparity between localities in terms of time costs and government dynamism shows that decentralization has not been closely linked to effective oversight mechanisms. Therefore, it is necessary to establish independent oversight mechanisms and publicize administrative reform indicators, considering this as a tool for institutional competition among localities. Standardizing procedural processes nationwide will limit discretion and ensure the uniformity of the investment environment.

Finally, the governance model needs to shift from a "risk control" mindset to a "facilitation" mindset. Widely applying post-audit mechanisms instead of pre-audits, expanding high-level online public services, and integrating data between agencies will help reduce time costs and informal costs for businesses. When public governance shifts towards service and partnership, the private sector's trust in the government will be strengthened, thereby improving the effectiveness of policy implementation.

3.3. Enhancing the Absorption Capacity and Internal Strength of the Private Sector

A good policy is only effective when businesses have sufficient absorption capacity. The fact that over 95% of Vietnamese businesses are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) shows that limitations in capital size, management, and technology remain major obstacles.

First, developing a long-term capital market is a fundamental condition for enhancing accumulation capacity. It is necessary to expand capital mobilization channels through a transparent stock market, strengthen the corporate bond market in a healthy direction, and increase credit guarantee funds for SMEs. Simultaneously, developing a venture capital ecosystem and innovation fund will create conditions for startups to access high-risk but essential financial resources for innovation.

Second, promoting value chain linkages and connecting FDI with domestic private enterprises is a crucial solution to transform integration into enhancing endogenous productivity. A national program is needed to develop domestic suppliers, support small businesses in achieving international standards, and establish mechanisms to encourage FDI enterprises to increase their localization rate. With improved linkages, the domestic private sector can access international technology, management standards, and markets.

Thirdly, enhancing governance capacity and innovation must become a long-term policy pillar. Implementing modern management training programs, supporting digital transformation, and providing tax incentives for R&D spending will help businesses shift from traditional family-based models to professional management models, thereby increasing their competitiveness in the digital and green economy.

3.4. Ensuring Synchronization Between the Three Groups of Factors

One of the core reasons why the effectiveness of policies for developing the private sector is not high is the lack of organic linkage between the three pillars (foundational institutions, public service implementation, and the absorption capacity of businesses). Legal reforms, if not accompanied by improvements in incentives and accountability for implementation, will continue to create a "policy gap"; conversely, if the administrative apparatus operates efficiently but businesses lack capital, technology, and modern management, reforms will be difficult to translate into productivity growth.

Therefore, the central solution is not just to improve individual elements but to design a unified national policy coordination mechanism. Specifically, it is necessary to establish an inter-sectoral coordinating focal point for private sector development under the Government, with the function of integrating investment, finance, innovation, and capital market development policies; ensuring consistency between the central and local levels. Simultaneously, a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system based on digitized data, interconnected between ministries, sectors, and localities, should be built with specific measurable indicators such as compliance costs, processing time, labor productivity, and participation in value chains.

Conducting periodic impact assessments and publicly disclosing the results will create pressure for improved implementation and provide a basis for timely policy adjustments. An evidence-based approach, with central coordination and clear accountability, will help ensure synergy between institutional reform, public governance, and strengthening the internal capacity of businesses, thereby enhancing policy effectiveness in the long term.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that the effectiveness of private sector development policies in Vietnam does not depend solely on individual policy tools but is simultaneously influenced by institutional structure, implementation quality, and the endogenous capacity of businesses. In recent years, Vietnam has made significant progress in institutional awareness and business environment reform; the private sector is expanding in scale and making substantial contributions to GDP and employment. However, limitations in the stability and predictability of laws, uneven implementation across localities, and the low productivity and innovation capacity of most businesses have undermined the overall effectiveness of the policies.

By adopting a multi-tiered theoretical framework of "design – implementation – absorption," this paper contributes to clarifying the systemic causes of the low effectiveness of private sector development policies. The key implication is that reforms need to be implemented synchronously and cohesively, linking the improvement of high-quality institutions, enhancing accountability and motivation in public service, while strengthening the governance, financial, and innovation capabilities of the private sector. Only

Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Private Economic Development Policies in Vietnam Today

when these three pillars operate harmoniously and are based on evidence-based coordination and oversight mechanisms can private sector development policies transform into drivers of productivity growth and enhance national competitiveness in the long term.

REFERENCES

- 1) Acemoglu, D. &. (2012). *Why nations fail: The origins of power, prosperity, and poverty*. Crown Publishing.
- 2) Cohen, W. M. (1990). Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35(1), 128–152.
- 3) Government. (2023). Report on the socio-economic situation in 2023. Hanoi.
- 4) Dunn, W. N. (2018). *Public Policy Analysis: An Integrated Approach* (6th ed.). Routledge. Retrieved from <https://www.routledge.com/Public-Policy-Analysis-An-Integrated-Approach/Dunn/p/book/9781138743847>.
- 5) Communist Party of Vietnam. (2021). Documents of the 13th National Congress of Delegates, Volume I. National Political Publishing House.
- 6) Mazmanian, P. A. (1972). The Prospects for Effective Implementation of Regulatory Policy. Retrieved from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4684-1155-3_1.
- 7) North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge University Press.
- 8) Nguyen Si Dung. (2025). Strong Development of the Private Economy - The Key to Double-Digit Growth. Retrieved from Government Electronic Newspaper: <https://xaydungchinhsach.chinhphu.vn/phat-trien-manh-kinh-te-tu-nhan-chia-khoa-de-tang-truong-2-con-so-119250308134537913.htm#:~:text=Kh%C3%B4ng%20nh%E1%BB%AFng%20th%E1%BA%BF%2C%20khu%20v%E1%BB%B1c,t%20nh%C3%A2n%20t%E1%BA%A1i%20Vi%E1%BB%87t%20Nam>.
- 9) OECD. (2018). *SME and entrepreneurship outlook 2018*. OECD Publishing. doi:https://doi.org/10.1787/sme_outlook-2018-en.
- 10) OECD. (2023). *SME and Entrepreneurship Policy in Vietnam 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- 11) Porter, M. E. (1990). *The competitive advantage of nations*. Free Press.
- 12) Pressman, J. L. (1984). *Implementation: How great expectations in Washington are dashed in Oakland* (3rd ed.). University of California Press.
- 13) Robinson, D. A. (2012). *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity and Poverty*. Crown Publishing.
- 14) General Statistics Office. (2023). *Vietnam Statistical Yearbook 2023*. Statistics Publishing House.
- 15) VCCI & USAID. (2023). *PCI and PGI index report 2023*. Retrieved from https://pcivietnam.vn/uploads/VN-Bao-cao-ngan-PCI/Bao-cao-ngan-2023_final.pdf
- 16) World Bank & MPI. (2016). *Vietnam 2035: Toward prosperity, creativity, equity, and democracy*. World Bank & MPI. Retrieved from <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/651001468190165513>
- 17) World Bank. (2020). *World development report 2020: Trading for development in the age of global value chains*. World Bank. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1457-0>
- 18) World Bank. (2022). *Viet Nam 2022 Country Private Sector Diagnostic: Creating Markets in Viet Nam*. World Bank Group.